

AN ANALYTICAL MODEL FOR PREDICTING THE TENSION MODULUS AND POISSON'S RATIO OF SATIN WEAVE COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Elastic properties, Micromechanics, Satin weave composite

ABSTRACT

Predicting elastic properties of braided composites is useful in aerospace structures. Previous methods used to predict elastic parameters are usually based on experimental databases or finite element methods. In this paper an attempt is made to establish an analytical model by combining the energy method and composite micromechanics based on representative volume element (RVE) for 8-harness satin weave composites to predict the tension modulus and Poisson's ratio.

The RVE of satin weave composites can be divided into three different sub unit cells: bending cells, semi-bending cells and straight cells. And the crimp of fiber yarns in these cells makes an influence on their tension properties. In this paper the minimum complementary energy principle (MCEP) is applied to calculate the tension modulus of bending yarns. With uniaxial external tension loading, interaction internal force and constraint moments being expressed as 0-order tensor T_i respectively (i is the number of force and moments), the total complementary energy of the RVE can be expressed by T_i . Then the MCEP gives the virtual displacement Δ_i of each virtual stress T_i . Thus the bending yarns tension modulus is obtained based on Δ_i and T_i .

According to the constitutive relations, principles of the strain in one direction being the same and the sum of the internal stress being zero, equations can be got on the relationship of the stress and strain in the fiber and matrix. Thus, the effective tension modulus and Poisson's ratio of satin weave composites can be calculated using the stress and strain of the fiber and matrix. Errors of the tension modulus and Poisson's ratio between analytical prediction and numerical simulation are smaller than 2%.

1. INTRODUCTION

Braided composites are new kinds of structural materials. These materials' advantages on strength, stiffness, anti-impact and good high temperature mechanical and thermal properties render the ideal for

use in thermal protection systems, rocket nozzles and other thermal structures in aerospace engineering. Although braided composites have several advantages, their micro-structures are more complex than laminates which contributes to the difficulty in computation to the mechanical properties of braided composites.

Several researchers^[1-4] have focused on the study of prediction for the elastic properties of braided composites. A common method to predict the modulus of braided composites of a simple RVE is stiffness averaging method^[5-7]. These researchers computed the effective mechanical properties by using component materials' properties and their volume fraction assuming that the strain of different component materials in one direction is the same. Facing the complex RVE, Kan^[8], Wu^[9], Mu^[10] and Guan^[11] divided it into several kinds of sub unit cells. The effective elastic properties of sub unit cells can be obtained easily by using the rule of mixtures formulations or stiffness averaging method and then the properties of the RVE are derived from the sub unit cells. Lu^[12] established the finite element model using the ABAQUS finite element analysis software to predict the tension behavior of plain weave composites with pores in the matrix. Xiong and Cheng^[13,14] established analytical models to predict the tension and compression modulus of 2-D plain weave composites based on the minimum complementary energy principle.

This article focuses on the study of prediction for the tension modulus and Poisson's ratio of satin weave composites. The author used the MCEP to calculate the reduction factor of fiber yarns modulus and improved traditional rule of mixtures formulations to obtain the elastic properties of the RVE. In addition, finite element models of the carbon-carbon composite material are established to prove the accuracy of analytical models.

2. GEOMETRIC DESCRIPTION OF THE RVE

The RVE of 8-harness satin weave composites consists of warp fiber yarns, weft fiber yarns and the matrix. A piece of satin cloth is formed with the interlacement of warp and weft yarns (shown in Fig.1^[8]) and the rest space is full of matrix. The mechanical behavior of the RVE depends on the properties of the fiber and matrix, the respective volume fraction, the type of weave and the geometry of the RVE.

Figure 1: The RVE of 8-harness satin weave composites

2.1. The properties of the fiber and matrix

The material of satin weave composite which this article focuses on is carbon/carbon. And elastic properties of the carbon fiber and carbon matrix are shown as Table 1^[15] and Table 2^[8] where the carbon fiber is symmetric anisotropy material and the matrix is isotropic material.

Longitudinal modulus E_{f1} (GPa)	Transverse modulus $E_{f2}=E_{f3}$ (GPa)	In-plane shear modulus $G_{f12}=G_{f13}$ (GPa)	Major Poisson's ratio $\nu_{f12}=\nu_{f13}$	Transverse Poisson's ratio ν_{f23}
230	15	15	0.2	0.07

Table 1: Carbon fiber properties

Modulus E_m (GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν_m
9.254	0.23

Table 2: Carbon matrix properties

2.2. The geometry of the RVE

Assumptions which are made about the geometry of the RVE include: 1. The shape of the cross-section of warp and weft yarns is idealized as a running track (shown in Fig.2); 2. The centerline of the yarn is composed of sinusoidal curves (just like s_{11} and s_{14} in Fig.3) and straight lines (just like s_{12} and s_{13} in Fig.3); 3. Warp and weft yarns go in the two orthogonal directions (shown in Fig.4); 4. Warp yarns in different satin cloths are parallel to each other.

Figure 2: The cross section of yarns

Figure 3: The undulation of yarns

Figure 4: Top view of the warp yarn and weft yarn

Geometric parameters of the yarn are shown in Table 3^[8].

Distance between the centerline of warp yarns l (mm)	Width of the cross-section of weft and warp yarns w (mm)	Thickness of the cross-section of weft and warp yarns t (mm)
1.3	0.6	0.2

Table 3: Geometric parameters of satin weave composites

From Fig1, it can be seen that the RVE of 8-harness satin weave composites is still not convenient to be used to compute mechanical properties. Referring to the study of Kan^[8], this article divided the RVE into three kinds of sub unit cells, which are bending cells, semi-bending cells and straight cells (shown in Fig.5). It should be noted that one sub unit cell is a cuboid while these illustrated in Fig.5 don't show the matrix. There exist the undulation of yarns in bending and semi-bending cells which makes influence on yarns' tension properties and the degree of the crimp depends upon geometric parameters shown in Table 3.

(a)Bending cell (b)Semi-bending cell (c)Straight cell
Figure 5: Sub unit cells of the RVE

2.3. The volume fraction of fiber and matrix

The width of one sub unit cell is equal to the distance between the centerline of warp yarns which is 1.3mm and the thickness is 0.46mm^[8] which is larger than the thickness that two yarns have since there are gaps between different satin cloths. And the sub unit cell volume is 0.7774mm³.

According to the area of cross-section and length in one sub unit cell, the volume fraction of fiber yarns can be obtained (shown in Table 4).

The fiber volume fraction in bending cell c_{f1}	The fiber volume fraction in semi-bending cell c_{f2}	The fiber volume fraction in straight cell c_{f3}
37.9%	37.4%	37.3%

Table 4: The fiber volume fraction in sub unit cells

3. PREDICTION TO THE TENSION MODULUS OF YARNS

There are totally three kinds of yarns in these sub unit cells which are bending yarns, semi-bending yarns and straight yarns. One bending cell has two bending yarns. One semi-bending cell has one semi-bending yarn and one straight yarn. And there are two straight yarns in one straight cell.

From Fig.2, the area and inertia of the cross-section of the yarn are, respectively,

$$A = t(w-t) + \frac{1}{4} \pi t^2 \quad (1)$$

$$I = \frac{1}{12} t^3 (w-t) + \frac{1}{64} \pi t^4 \quad (2)$$

Referring to the article [13], the MCEP can give the effective tension modulus of bending fiber. The warp yarn in the bending sub unit cell can be simplified as beams consist of sinusoidal curves and straight lines (shown in Fig.3).

The mathematical functions of the four curve sections of warp yarn in Fig.3 can be expressed, respectively, as

$$s_{11} : z_{11} = \frac{t}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{l-w+t}\right), \left(0 \leq x \leq \frac{l-w+t}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$s_{12} : z_{12} = \frac{t}{2}, \left(\frac{l-w+t}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{l}{2}\right) \quad (4)$$

$$s_{13} : z_{13} = \frac{t}{2}, \left(\frac{l}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{l+w-t}{2}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$s_{14} : z_{14} = \frac{t}{2} \sin\left[\frac{\pi}{l-w+t}(x-w+t)\right], \left(\frac{l+w-t}{2} \leq x \leq l\right) \quad (6)$$

And the mathematical functions of the weft yarn are analogous to those of the warp yarn and expressed as

$$s_{21} : z_{21} = -\frac{t}{2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{l-w+t}\right), \left(0 \leq y \leq \frac{l-w+t}{2}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$s_{22} : z_{22} = -\frac{t}{2}, \left(\frac{l-w+t}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{l}{2}\right) \quad (8)$$

$$s_{23} : z_{23} = -\frac{t}{2}, \left(\frac{l}{2} \leq y \leq \frac{l+w-t}{2}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$s_{24} : z_{24} = \frac{t}{2} \sin\left[\frac{\pi}{l-w+t}(y-w+t)\right], \left(\frac{l+w-t}{2} \leq y \leq l\right) \quad (10)$$

The tangent of off-axial angle θ_{ij} of the warp yarn is obtained as

$$\tan \theta_{1j} = \frac{dz_{1j}}{dx}, (j=1,2,3,4) \quad (11)$$

Given there exists a uniaxial tension loading T_1 in the section of warp yarn, the interaction internal force T_2 and constraint moments T_3, T_4 are forced on the warp and weft yarn (shown in Fig.6).

Figure 6: (a) Forces on the warp yarn (b) Forces on the weft yarn

According to mechanical theory, in the bending cell, the cross-section moments in the warp and weft yarn and cross-section forces in the warp yarn can be obtained as

a) the cross-section moment in the warp yarn

$$s_{11} : M_{11}(x) = z_{11}T_1 + T_3 \quad (12)$$

$$s_{12} : M_{12}(x) = z_{12}T_1 + \frac{T_2}{2} \left(x - \frac{l-w+t}{2} \right)^2 + T_3 \quad (13)$$

b) the cross-section force in the warp yarn

$$s_{11}, s_{12} : N_{1j} = \frac{T_{1j}}{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \theta_{1j}}}, (j=1,2) \quad (14)$$

c) the cross-section moment in the weft yarn

$$s_{21} : M_{21} = T_4 \quad (15)$$

$$s_{22} : M_{22} = -\frac{T_2}{2} \left(y - \frac{l-w+t}{2} \right)^2 + T_4 \quad (16)$$

Because of the yarns symmetry, the distribution of the cross-section moments and forces in s_{13}, s_{14}, s_{23} and s_{24} are the same as the above.

Then the complementary strain energy of yarns is

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{E_{f1}I_{s_{1j}}} \int M_{1j}^2 dl + \frac{1}{E_{f1}A_{s_{1j}}} \int N_{1j}^2 dl + \frac{1}{E_{f1}I_{s_{2j}}} \int M_{2j}^2 dl, (j=1,2) \quad (17)$$

T_k can be considered as 0-order tensors and the tensor form expression of the complementary strain energy Π will be got which is

$$\Pi = \lambda_{kl} T_k \bullet T_l, (k, l=1,2,3,4) \quad (18)$$

where λ_{kl} only has relationship with component materials properties and geometry parameters of the RVE.

The MCEP gives

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial T_1} = K_{11}T_1 + K_{12}T_2 + K_{13}T_3 = \Delta \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial T_k} = K_{kl}T_l = 0, (k=2,3,4, l=1,2,3,4) \quad (20)$$

where K_{kl} only has relationship with component materials properties and geometry parameters of the RVE and Δ is the virtual displacement of T_1 .

From Eq.(19) and Eq.(20), Eq.(21) can be obtained as

$$\frac{\Delta}{T_1} = W \quad (21)$$

where W only has relationship with component materials properties and geometry parameters of the RVE.

Thus the modulus reduction factor of the warp yarn in the bending sub unit cell is

$$\eta = \frac{l}{A'W} \quad (22)$$

where A' represents for the section area of the end portion which is

$$A' = A \sqrt{1 + \left[\frac{\pi t}{2(l-w+t)} \right]^2} \quad (23)$$

The modulus reduction factor of the straight yarn is equal to 1 and the reduction factor of the semi-bending yarn can be defined as the average of 1 and η derived from Eq.(22). That is

$$\eta' = \frac{\eta + 1}{2} \quad (24)$$

According to Eq.(22) and Eq.(24), the modulus reduction factor of the three kinds of yarns are gained which are shown in Table 5.

Modulus reduction factor of the bending yarn	Modulus reduction factor of the semi-bending yarn	Modulus reduction factor of the straight yarn
0.7468	0.8734	1

Table 5: Modulus reduction factor of the three kinds of yarns

4. ANALYTICAL PREDICTION TO THE PROPERTIES OF THE RVE

4.1. Prediction to the properties of sub unit cells

Traditional rule of mixtures formulations cannot apply the prediction for the sub unit cell accurately. The sub unit cell can be divided into an above part and a below part (shown in Fig.7).

With uniaxial loading, assumptions are made: 1. The strain of the two parts in one direction are the same; 2. The sum of the internal stress is zero.

Figure 7: Division of the sub unit cell

According to the above assumptions, with uniaxial loading F in Direction 1, equations can be obtained as

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{\sigma_{f1}}{\eta_1 E_{f1}} - \frac{\nu_{f21}}{E_{f2}} \sigma_2 \quad (25)$$

$$\varepsilon_1 = \frac{\sigma_{m1}}{E_m} - \frac{\nu_m}{E_m} \sigma_2 \quad (26)$$

$$\varepsilon_1 = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{E_{f2}} - \frac{v_{f12}}{\eta_2 E_{f1}} \sigma_{f2} \right) c_f + \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{E_m} - \frac{v_m}{E_m} \sigma_{m2} \right) c_m \quad (27)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{E_{f2}} - \frac{v_{f12}}{\eta_1 E_{f1}} \sigma_{f1} \right) c_f + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{E_m} - \frac{v_m}{E_m} \sigma_{m1} \right) c_m \quad (28)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{\sigma_{f2}}{\eta_2 E_{f1}} - \frac{v_{f21}}{E_{f2}} \sigma_1 \quad (29)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = \frac{\sigma_{m2}}{E_m} - \frac{v_m}{E_m} \sigma_1 \quad (30)$$

$$\sigma_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + \sigma_{f2} \cdot \frac{c_f}{2} + \sigma_{m2} \cdot \frac{c_m}{2} = 0 \quad (31)$$

where c_f and c_m are the volume fraction of the fiber and matrix, respectively (shown in Table 4); η_1 and η_2 represent for the modulus reduction factor of the yarn in Direction 1 and 2, respectively (shown in Table 5).

Eq.(25)-(31) can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \mathbf{b}\varepsilon_1 \quad (32)$$

where

$$\mathbf{x} = [\sigma_{f1} \quad \sigma_{m1} \quad \sigma_1 \quad \sigma_{f2} \quad \sigma_{m2} \quad \sigma_2 \quad \varepsilon_2]^T \quad (33)$$

\mathbf{A} is a constant matrix and \mathbf{b} is a constant vector both of which only have the relationship with the properties of materials and their volume fraction.

According to Kramer law, \mathbf{x} can be obtained as

$$x_i = \frac{|\mathbf{A}_i|}{|\mathbf{A}|} \quad (34)$$

where \mathbf{A}_i comes from the i^{th} row of \mathbf{A} being replaced by $\mathbf{b}\varepsilon_1$ in turn.

Eq.(35) can be derived from Eq.(34).

$$\mathbf{x} = [P_1 \quad P_2 \quad P_3 \quad P_4 \quad P_5 \quad P_6 \quad P_7]^T \varepsilon_1 \quad (35)$$

Thus the effective tension modulus in Direction 1 and Poisson's ratio of the sub unit cell can be derived from Eq.(35).

$$E_1^{\text{cell}} = \frac{1}{2} (c_f P_1 + c_m P_2 + P_3) \quad (36)$$

$$v_{21}^{\text{cell}} = -P_7 \quad (37)$$

In the bending cell and straight cell, the effective tension modulus and effective Poisson's ratio in Direction 1 and Direction 2 is equal to each other. In the semi-bending cell, analogous calculation procedure with uniaxial loading in Direction 2 is made since the effective tension modulus and effective Poisson's ratio in the two direction is different from each other.

4.2. Prediction to the properties of the RVE

The RVE of 8-harness satin weave composites can be divided into 64 sub unit cells which include 8 bending sub unit cells, 24 straight sub unit cells and 32 semi-bending sub unit cells in half of which the semi-bending yarn is parallel to Direction 1 and in the rest of which the semi-bending yarn is parallel to Direction 2. According to the rule of mixtures formulations, the effective modulus and Poisson's ratio of the RVE can be obtained as

$$E_1^{\text{eff}} = c_{c1} E_1^{\text{cell1}} + \frac{1}{2} c_{c2} E_1^{\text{cell2}} + \frac{1}{2} c_{c2} E_2^{\text{cell2}} + c_{c3} E_1^{\text{cell3}} \quad (38)$$

$$v_{21}^{\text{eff}} = c_{c1} v_{21}^{\text{cell1}} + \frac{1}{2} c_{c2} v_{21}^{\text{cell2}} + \frac{1}{2} c_{c2} v_{12}^{\text{cell2}} + c_{c3} v_{21}^{\text{cell3}} \quad (39)$$

where c_{c1} , c_{c2} , c_{c3} represent for the volume fraction of bending cell, semi-bending cell and straight cell which are 12.5%, 50% and 37.5%, respectively; E_1^{cell1} , E_1^{cell3} represent for the tension modulus of bending cell and straight cell respectively; E_1^{cell2} represents for the tension modulus of semi-bending cell in the direction to which the semi-bending yarn is parallel and E_2^{cell2} is the tension modulus in the other

direction; ν_{21}^{cell1} , ν_{21}^{cell3} represent for Poisson's ratio of bending cell and straight cell respectively; ν_{21}^{cell2} represent for Poisson's ratio of semi-bending cell in the direction to which the semi-bending yarn is parallel and ν_{12}^{cell2} is Poisson's ratio in the other direction.

5. NUMERICAL SIMULATION AND COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMULATION AND ANALYTICAL PREDICTIONS

5.1. Numerical simulation

Numerical models of the three kinds of sub unit cells are established by using ABAQUS finite element analysis software. The three kinds of sub unit cells are divided by tetrahedral elements (C3D4) (shown in Fig.8).

Figure 8: Elements of the sub unit cell

In the numerical model of sub unit cells, the periodic boundary condition is that different nodes on one surface have the same normal deform. The deform boundary condition is exerted in the bending cell and straight cell which is that the deform of one surface whose normal direction is parallel to Direction 1 is 0.0013mm and the deform of other surfaces whose normal direction is parallel to Direction 1 or 2 is zero. Two calculation procedure are made for the semi-bending cell. Uniaxial load is forced in Direction 1 and Direction 2, respectively, in the two calculation procedure. The constitutive equations of the sub unit cell are

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_2} \\ -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{E_2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

E_1 and ν_{12} can be derived from ε_1 , ε_2 , σ_1 , σ_2 . ε_1 just results from the deform of Direction 1 which is equal to $1000\mu\varepsilon$ and ε_2 is zero. σ_1 and σ_2 are derived from reaction forces in Direction 1 or 2 which are the result of numerical simulation (shown in Table 6~8).

$$\sigma_i = \frac{RF_i}{lh} \quad (41)$$

where RF_i represents for the reaction force shown in Table 6-8, l is the width of the sub unit cell which is equal to 1.3mm and h is the thickness of the sub unit cell which is equal to 0.46mm.

Reaction force in Direction 1 (N)	Reaction force in Direction 2 (N)
26.9532	1.50211

Table 6: Reaction force of the bending cell

Reaction force in Direction 1 with	Reaction force in Direction 2 with	Reaction force in Direction 1 with	Reaction force in Direction 1 with
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loading in Direction 1 (N)	loading in Direction 1 (N)	loading in Direction 2 (N)	loading in Direction 2 (N)
28.6910	1.48959	1.48959	30.9299

Table 7: Reaction force of the semi-bending cell

Reaction force in Direction 1 (N)	Reaction force in Direction 2 (N)
30.9215	1.50316

Table 8: Reaction forces of the straight cell

5.2. Comparison between analytical prediction and numerical simulation

Eq.(36) and Eq.(37) give the analytical prediction results of the tension modulus and Poisson's ratio (shown in Table 9-11).

Effective tension modulus of the bending cell E_1^{cell1} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the bending cell ν_{21}^{cell1}
41.207	0.0572

Table 9: Analytical prediction for properties of the bending cell

Effective tension modulus of the semi- bending cell in Direction 1 E_1^{cell2} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the semi- bending cell in Direction 1 ν_{21}^{cell2}	Effective tension modulus of the semi- bending cell in Direction 2 E_2^{cell2} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the semi- bending cell in Direction 2 ν_{12}^{cell2}
46.258	0.0476	51.705	0.0521

Table 10: Analytical prediction for properties of the semi-bending cell

It should be noticed that Direction 1 in the semi-bending cell is parallel to the semi-bending yarn and Direction 2 is parallel to the straight yarn.

Effective tension modulus of the straight cell E_1^{cell3} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the straight cell ν_{21}^{cell3}
51.599	0.0477

Table 11: Analytical prediction for properties of the straight cell

According to Eq.38 and Eq.39, analytical prediction for the tension modulus of the RVE is 48.99GP and Poisson's ratio is 0.0500.

Table 12-14 illustrate the numerical simulation results of these properties which are derived from Table 6-8 and Eq.(41).

Effective tension modulus of the bending cell E_1^{cell1} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the bending cell ν_{21}^{cell1}
44.932	0.0557

Table 12: Numerical simulation results of properties of the bending cell

Effective tension modulus of the semi- bending cell in Direction 1 E_1^{cell2} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the semi- bending cell in Direction 1 ν_{21}^{cell2}	Effective tension modulus of the semi- bending cell in Direction 2 E_2^{cell2} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the semi- bending cell in Direction 2 ν_{12}^{cell2}
47.858	0.0482	51.593	0.0519

Table 13: Numerical simulation results of properties of the semi-bending cell

The definition of Direction 1,2 is the same as Table 10.

Effective tension modulus of the straight cell E_1^{cell3} (GPa)	Effective Poisson's ratio of the straight cell ν_{21}^{cell3}
51.586	0.0486

Table 14: Numerical simulation results of properties of the straight cell

According to Eq.38 and Eq.39, numerical simulation results of the tension modulus of the RVE is 49.82GPa and Poisson's ratio is 0.0502. The error between analytical prediction and numerical simulation is shown as Table 15.

The error of the tension modulus	The error of Poisson's ratio
1.69%	0.40%

Table 15: Errors of the tension modulus and Poisson's ratio

6. CONCLUSIONS

The main idea of this paper is to establish an analytical model to predict the tension modulus and Poisson's ratio. The author applies the minimum complementary energy principle and improves the rule of mixtures formulations. According to the comparison between the results of analytical model and finite element model, this analytical method has been proved to be effective.

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